

ON A FEW ADDITIONAL CONSIDERATIONS FOR APPLYING DENSITY-TYPE TOPOLOGY OPTIMIZATION TO THE CASE OF ADDITIVE MANUFACTURING OF FIBER REINFORCED COMPOSITES

Kohji SUZUKI¹

¹ Chiba Institute of Technology, Department of Mechanical Engineering,
2-17-1 Tsudanuma, Narashino-shi, 275-0016 Chiba, Japan

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ABSTRACT

Topology optimization designs are very attractive for additive manufacturing product designs. However, this well-proved method still seems not to be perfect in case that one tries to apply it to fiber reinforced composite materials design, in which one should take into consideration their orthotropic and graded material and physical properties. In this study, the present author tries to raise awareness of this issue and also attempts to formulate an extension or a generalization of the existing density-based topology optimization scheme, that is, SIMP (Solid Isotropic Material with Penalization) method.

1 INTRODUCTION

Recently, additive manufacturing, or 3D printing, of fiber reinforced composite materials has been attracting more and more attentions in various industrial fields such as aerospace, automotive, civil and so on. In addition, more and more people have been recognizing that the topology optimization design methodologies will be able to be used as powerful tools for finding more rational and cost- and weight-saving structural components combined with additive manufacturing, such as fused deposition modelling (FDM) 3D printers. By the way, fiber reinforced composites such as carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) are inherently different from the conventional structural materials and processing like steel and aluminium alloy for turning and milling machinings (that is, conventional subtractive manufacturing methods) in that they have possibly orthotropic and gradient material properties when processed with additive manufacturing tools. Therefore, it will be quite beneficial that ones think of some improvement of the mathematical formulations and computational algorism in terms of topology optimization [1, 2] in order to suit it to the case of additive manufacturing of fiber reinforced composites.

In this paper, the author tried to suggest a few ideas of his own for the above-mentioned technical topic. The first one is about allowing intermediate density (grey results) in the final optimization results since in additive manufacturing of fiber reinforced composites, crude density portions which are not crucial in terms of overall structural integrity may be realistic. The second one is about relaxation of design variable domain definition in order to enhance density in the portion where more reinforcement is necessary. The last one is about considering orthotropic materials properties since as already mentioned fiber reinforced composites essentially have a drastic difference in elastic and strength properties between the longitudinal (that is fiber reinforcing) and transverse directions. From a typical numerical example, the present suggestions of the author's own will be shown to be quite rational and effective to find better topology optimized structural components molded with any additive manufacturing techniques.

2 THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

2.1 Structural optimization process with a general-purpose FEM code

In Fig.1, an overall flow chart of the typical structural optimization process with a help of design sensitivity analysis that is implemented in general purpose FEM codes, such as MSC Nastran and ANSYS, is shown [3]. First, at the block of **A** part, design variables, $\mathbf{X} = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_N\}$, an objective function to be optimized (minimized), $f(\mathbf{X})$, a main constraint function, $g_j(\mathbf{X}) \leq 0$, and also two side constraint functions, $g_{LB}(x_i) \leq 0$ and $g_{UB}(x_i) \leq 0$, are respectively defined to the FEM numerical model. After that, appropriate initial values $\mathbf{X}^{(0)} = \{x_1^{(0)}, x_2^{(0)}, \dots, x_N^{(0)}\}$ are assigned to the design variables and then optimization iterations (design cycles) begin.

In the block of **B** part, a single ordinal numerical structural analysis is carried out and a global nodal displacement solutions, $\mathbf{U}^{(k)} = \mathbf{K}^{-1}(\mathbf{X}^{(k)}) \cdot \mathbf{F}$, are obtained, where $\mathbf{K}(\mathbf{X}^{(k)})$ is the global stiffness matrix generated and assembled based on the design variables at k^{th} iteration, $\mathbf{X}^{(k)} = \{x_1^{(k)}, x_2^{(k)}, \dots, x_N^{(k)}\}$, and \mathbf{F} is the global nodal force vector, which is usually to be constant during the whole design cycles. Once the global nodal displacements at k^{th} iteration, $\mathbf{U}^{(k)}$, have been determined, subsequent quantities such as stress and strain can also be evaluated and then k^{th} values of the objective and the main constraint functions, $f(\mathbf{X}^{(k)}, \mathbf{U}^{(k)})$, and, $g_j(\mathbf{X}^{(k)}, \mathbf{U}^{(k)})$, can be determined as design responses in terms of $\mathbf{X}^{(k)}$. After examining whether the k^{th} objective function, $f(\mathbf{X}^{(k)}, \mathbf{U}^{(k)})$, has reached a convergence or not, the iteration will be stopped when a convergence has obtained, or, otherwise, will be continued and the program run goes on to the design sensitivity analysis section. In this section, by using the forward difference approximation, design sensitivities of the objective function and the constraint functions in terms of the k^{th} design variables are respectively calculated as follows,

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \frac{\partial f}{\partial \mathbf{X}} \Big|_{\mathbf{X}^{(k)}} &\simeq \frac{f(\mathbf{X}^{(k)}, \mathbf{U}^{(k)}) - f(\mathbf{X}^{(k-1)}, \mathbf{U}^{(k-1)})}{\Delta \mathbf{X}} \\ \frac{\partial g_j^*}{\partial \mathbf{X}} \Big|_{\mathbf{X}^{(k)}} &\simeq \frac{g_j^*(\mathbf{X}^{(k)}, \mathbf{U}^{(k)}) - g_j^*(\mathbf{X}^{(k-1)}, \mathbf{U}^{(k-1)})}{\Delta \mathbf{X}} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (1)$$

After collecting all the data necessary for the present optimization seeking, in the block of **C** part, a numerical optimization loop to the k^{th} approximate model will be conducted to obtain next $(k+1)^{\text{th}}$ updated design variables, $\mathbf{X}^{(k+1)}$, objective function, $f^{(k+1)}$, and constraint functions, $g_i^{(k+1)}$. The aforementioned optimization problem can be categorized as general nonlinear ones of large number of variables and with constrains and will be able to be solved by non-linear iterative algorithms such as the sequential quadratic programming.

Figure 1: The typical flow chart of structural optimization process for a linear static problem.

2.2 Topology optimization process with the density method (SIMP method)

As one of the structural optimization types, topology optimization is used in this study. In this optimization scheme, one defines design variables at all the finite elements in the optimization region as so-called characteristic functions, which ideally takes either of binary integers, 0 or 1. When it takes 0 as its design value, then its finite element is to be looked upon as vanished, that is, no material there. However, due to numerical difficulty occurring when one tries to enforce the variables to be rigorously binary, the design space are usually relaxed by introducing so-called normalized densities, x_i , as the approximate design variables, each of which takes continuous value between 0 and 1. This method is called the density method, or, SIMP (Solid Isotropic Material with Penalization) method since this method uses so-called a penalization parameter (penalty factor), p , which makes intermediate values (other than 0 or 1) more costly for the design variables to take.

As already mentioned, in the density method (SIMP method), so-called normalized densities, $x_{\min} \leq x_i \leq 1$ ($i=1,2,\dots,N$), are defined at all the finite element (total number of them is N) in the topology optimization design region, D , as the design variables. Therefore, during the optimization process, each stiffness of the finite element is updated as follows,

$$E_i = x_i^p E_0, \quad x_i = x_{\min} \approx 0 \Rightarrow \text{void}, \quad x_i = 1 \Rightarrow \text{solid} \quad (2)$$

where E_0 is the original stiffness and $p > 1$ is the penalty parameter.

When one wants to minimize the mean compliance (as long as loads are kept constant, this means to maximize the global stiffness) as the objective function while mass reduction ratio as the main constraint function, the problem descriptions can be stated as,

$$\left. \begin{aligned}
&\text{design variables: normalized density} \quad \mathbf{x} = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_N\} \\
&\text{objective function: mean compliance} \quad c(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{f}^T \mathbf{u} = \sum_{i=1}^N \mathbf{u}_i^T \mathbf{K}_i(x_i) \mathbf{u}_i \\
&\text{main constraint: mass target} \quad g(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{i=1}^N V_i \rho_i - M_{\text{target}} V_0 \rho_0 \\
&\quad \quad \quad = \sum_{i=1}^N V_i x_i \rho_0 - M_{\text{target}} V_0 \rho_0 = \left(\sum_{i=1}^N V_i x_i - V_{\text{target}} \right) \rho_0 \leq 0 \\
&\text{side constraints:} \quad g_i^{\text{low}} = x_{\min} - x_i \leq 0, g_i^{\text{up}} = x_i - 1 \leq 0
\end{aligned} \right\} \quad (3)$$

and

$$\min_{\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^N} \left\{ c(\mathbf{x}) \mid g(\mathbf{x}) \leq 0, \mathbf{g}^{\text{low}} \leq \mathbf{0}, \mathbf{g}^{\text{up}} \leq \mathbf{0} \right\} \quad (4)$$

The above problem statement is suitable for seeking some structural forms which minimize stiffness reductions under a certain weight limitation and this is also fit to the topic of the present study, that is, to search for some new light-weight forms in layered and sandwich-type FRP composite structures.

2.3 A few additional considerations in the case of fiber reinforced composites

In this study, the author tried to suggest a few ideas of his own for the above-mentioned technical topic. The first one is about allowing intermediate density (grey results) in the final optimization results since in additive manufacturing of fiber reinforced composites, crude density portions which are not crucial in terms of overall structural integrity may be realistic. The second one is about relaxation of design variable domain definition in order to enhance density in the portion where more reinforcement is necessary. The last one is about considering orthotropic materials properties since as already mentioned fiber reinforced composites essentially have a drastic difference in elastic and strength properties between the longitudinal (that is fiber reinforcing) and transverse directions. From a typical numerical example, the present suggestions of the author's own will be shown to be quite rational and effective to find better topology optimized structural components molded with any additive manufacturing techniques.

$$\left. \begin{aligned}
&\text{Young's Modulus in Longitudinal (Fiber) Direction: } E_L \\
&\text{Young's Modulus in Transverse Direction: } E_T \\
&\text{Major and Minor Poisson's Ratios: } \frac{\nu_{LT}}{E_L} = \frac{\nu_{TL}}{E_T} \\
&\text{Degree of Orthotropic Modulus: } \alpha = \frac{E_L}{E_T} \\
&\text{Assumption on Shear Modulus: } G_{LT} = \frac{E_T}{2(1 + \nu_{LT})}
\end{aligned} \right\} \quad (5)$$

3 NUMERICAL EXAMPLES

As a typical case study, the three-point bending problem shown in Fig.2, which has been extensively discussed in the conventional topology optimization community for more than a few decades, was used with the so-called degree of orthotropy, α , varied by 0.1, 1 and 10 in order to take materials orthotropic properties into consideration. In Fig.3, topology optimized density distributions are shown for different α values. As shown in these result, considering material orthotropy will give different results as compared to the conventional isotropic case shown in Fig.3(b). It is interesting that as the degree of orthotropy increases in magnitude, the sharpness of the optimized shape seems to be

increased. It may be one of the first results and discussion on considering orthotropic material properties in the context of density-type topology optimization procedure although some results exist in cases of topology optimization by using the homogenization method.

Figure 2: Typical case study: MBB problem.

(a) $\alpha = 0.1$

(b) $\alpha = 1$

(c) $\alpha = 10$

Figure 3: MBB problems considering orthotropic elasticity.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, the author tried to suggest a few ideas of his own for the above-mentioned technical topic. From a typical numerical example, the present suggestions of the author's own will be shown to be quite rational and effective to find better topology optimized structural components molded with any additive manufacturing techniques.

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